

Original Article

Requirements of Routine Maintenance Dose of Phenobarbitone after Loading Dose in Perinatal Asphyxia with Hypoxic-Ischemic Encephalopathy Stage 2: A Hospital Based Study in Bangladesh

Bidhan Chandra Biswas¹, Muzibur Rahman², Zahid Hassan Arefin³, Kamrul Ahsan Khan², Rumpa Moni Chowdhury⁴, Jamshed Alam⁴, Arjun Chandra Dey⁵, Sanjoy Kumer Dey⁵, Abid Hossain Mollah⁶, Md. A. Mannan⁷, Mohammad Shahidullah⁸

Abstract

Background: Hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE), secondary to perinatal asphyxia is the single most common cause of neonatal seizures in both full term and premature infants. Phenobarbitone is a potent sedative and powerful anticonvulsant, and the most frequently used first line treatment for neonatal seizures worldwide, which is given to the neonate initially as a large loading dose to stop convulsion followed by a low maintenance dose to prevent recurrence of convulsion.

Objective: To determine the necessity of routine maintenance dose of phenobarbitone (after loading dose) to prevent recurrence of seizures in perinatal asphyxia with HIE stage 2.

Methodology: A randomized controlled trial performed in Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU) over a period of one year. A total of 60 neonates, diagnosed as perinatal asphyxia with HIE stage 2 were included in the study and randomized to intervention group (group A) and control group (group B), 30 cases each. Group A received loading dose only, and group B received conventional treatment (i.e. loading plus maintenance dose). Initial loading dose was intravenous phenobarbitone 20mg/kg. A second or third loading dose of 10mg/kg was given at 30minute interval if convulsion persisted; maximum 40mg/kg of phenobarbitone was given as loading dose. In group B, loading doses were given in the same manner, followed by first maintenance dose of 5 mg/kg after 12 hour of last loading dose and maintained at every 24hour interval. Serum phenobarbitone level was measured 30 min after the last loading dose in group A and first maintenance dose in group B.

Results: Age, sex, mode and place of delivery, duration of labor, birth weight, gestational age etc. were similar in both groups. Serum phenobarbitone levels were in a strong positive linear relationship in both groups. The mean serum phenobarbitone levels corresponding to their initial doses were 25µg/ml, 40 µg/ml or 55 µg/ml in group A ($r = 0.841$) and 26µg/ml, 47 µg/ml or 66 µg/ml in group B ($r = 0.880$). Recurrence of seizures after initial control occurred in 13% in group A Vs 10% cases in group B ($p = 0.68$). The mean value of seizure recurrence time were 12.67 ± 3.06 hours in group A and 11.50 ± 4.36 hours in group B ($p = 0.71$).

Conclusion: No statistically significant difference was observed in recurrence of seizures between two groups, So maintenance dose of phenobarbitone (after loading dose) is presumably unnecessary to prevent recurrence of neonatal seizures in asphyxiated newborns of HIE stage 2.

Key words: Perinatal Asphyxia, HIE, Phenobarbitone

1. Asstt. Professor, Dept. of Neonatology. Sher-E-Bangla Medical College, Barisal.
 2. Asstt. Professor, Dept. of Pediatrics. Institute of Child and Mother Health, Matuail, Dhaka.
 3. Asstt. Professor, Epidemiology and Biostatistics. ICMH.
 4. MD Residency Student. Neonatology. BSMMU.
 5. Associate Professor, Neonatology. BSMMU.
 6. Professor & Head, Dept. of Neonatology. DMCH.
 7. Professor Neonatology. BSMMU.
 8. Professor & Chairman. Dept. of Neonatology & Pro. Vice Chancellor, BSMMU.
- Correspondence:** Dr. Bidhan Chandra Biswas. Asstt. Professor, Dept. of Neonatology. Sher-E-Bangla Medical College, Barisal. Cell No: 01711448764, 01556634030.

Introduction:

Over four million newborns die every year, with most (98%) of the deaths occurring in the developing world. Perinatal asphyxia, low birth weight, prematurity and sepsis related problems are the major causes of death.¹ In Bangladesh major causes of neonatal deaths are perinatal asphyxia (28%), preterm birth complications (26%), and neonatal infection (25%).² About 21,500 newborns die each year in Bangladesh due to severe perinatal asphyxia.³

Phenobarbitone is a potent sedative as well as a powerful anticonvulsant and it remains the most frequently used first line treatment for neonatal seizures worldwide.⁴ It is given to babies with perinatal asphyxia with seizures for seizure control as well as protecting brain. But phenobarbitone has side effects. It has long been known to have long term effects on brain growth.⁵⁻⁷ It sedates babies, suppressing clinical manifestations of seizures.⁸ Apnea and hypotension may occur with concomitant use of benzodiazepines. In our routine practice after initial control of convulsion with loading dose of phenobarbitone, maintenance dose is continued for up to 5-7 days. But therapeutic serum level of phenobarbitone is achieved after loading dose of phenobarbitone.⁹ Because anticonvulsive drugs may have detrimental effects on the developing brain, they should be discontinued as soon as possible. Phenobarbitone causes retarded brain growth in rats.¹⁰ Long term phenobarbitone (after loading dose) therapy may lead to inhibition of brain development. In most newborns, seizures stop when the acute encephalopathy is over.¹¹ Therefore, the routine use of maintenance dose of phenobarbitone therapy to prevent recurrence of seizures after initial control of seizure following perinatal asphyxia needs to be evaluated. So the objective of this study was to determine the necessity of routine maintenance dose of phenobarbitone (after loading dose) to prevent recurrence of seizures in perinatal asphyxia with HIE stage 2.

Materials and Methods:

This was a randomized clinical trial conducted in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) of BSMMU over a period of one year from January 2013 to December 2013. Sample has been collected from the NICU of BSMMU and Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Dhaka. During the study period, a total of 60 neonates diagnosed as perinatal asphyxia with HIE stage 2 fulfilling

the inclusion and exclusion criteria has been enrolled purposively after informed parental consent and later on randomly allocated into two groups by sealed envelope method, which was taken by the parents from a box containing 60 sealed envelope labeling 30 as case and 30 as control. Before opening the envelope neither the investigator nor the parent was aware in which group they will be enrolled. Thirty newborns in the intervention group (Group A) has received loading dose of phenobarbitone only and 30 newborns in the control group (Group B) has received loading plus maintenance dose of phenobarbitone.

Inclusion criteria:

Term or late preterm newborns with perinatal asphyxia presented with seizures (HIE stage 2), between 34 to 42 weeks of gestation, who got admitted in the hospital within 24 hours of birth.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Status epilepticus.
2. Electrolytes abnormality.
3. Hypoglycemia--- Blood sugar < 2.6 mmol/L.
4. Gross CNS anomalies like anencephaly, meningocele, meningomyelocele, meningoencephalocele.
5. Patients received anticonvulsive treatment before enrolment.
6. Asphyxiated babies whose seizures were not controlled by loading dose of phenobarbitone only i.e. those required phenytoin and or midazolam.
7. History of maternal risk factors for sepsis (prolonged rupture of membrane more than 18 hours, fever, urinary tract infection, lower abdominal tenderness, foul smelling lochial discharge, or meconium stained amniotic fluid).
8. After enrollment, detailed history regarding chronological age in hours, history of delayed cry after birth, seizure, gestational age, inborn/ out born status, presence of any co morbidities were recorded by a structured questionnaire. Birth weight was measured by digital weighing scale (SALTER-914) with error of up to $\pm$ 10gm. Gestational age was determined by history and maternal ultrasound examination report done during 1st trimester of pregnancy, if available. The patients were then randomized either group-A or group-B.

For both group-A and group-B, patient's seizures were controlled by loading dose of phenobarbitone (20mg/kg or 30mg/kg or 40mg/kg). Initially 20mg/kg was given, then the baby was observed for 30 minutes. If seizures persist, a 2nd loading dose of phenobarbitone (10 mg/kg) was given and a 3rd loading dose (10 mg/kg) was given again after 30 minutes if required. Total 40 mg /kg phenobarbitone was given as loading dose if necessary. Then in group A, no maintenance dose of phenobarbitone was administered. In group B (Control) a 5 mg/kg maintenance dose of phenobarbitone was administered slowly intravenously after 12 hours of last loading dose and it was maintained every 24 hourly for the period of hospital stay.¹²

Blood sample (3ml) was drawn after 30 min of giving last loading dose (Group A) and after 30 minutes of giving first maintenance dose (Group B). Serum phenobarbitone was measured by the AxSYM Phenobarbital assay which utilized Fluorescence Polarization Immunoassay (FPIA) technology in The Department of Biochemistry of BSMMU.

Seizure recurrence was observed and the time was calculated from the completion of last loading dose of phenobarbitone to clinical recurrence. The babies were observed for 48 hours. Two groups were compared by the 'seizure recurrence number' and the 'seizure recurrence time'- the time from the last loading dose of phenobarbitone to recurrence of seizure.

Operational Definitions:

Initial control of seizure: 'Seizure is controlled initially' if there is no seizure within 30 min of observation period after completion of the last drug administration.

Full control of seizure: 'Seizure is controlled fully' if there is 48 hours seizure free period after completion of the last drug administration.

Seizure recurrence time: The time from the last loading dose of phenobarbitone to recurrence of seizure.

Seizure recurrence number: Number of babies in group A or Group B those seizures were recurred in the first 48 hours after stabilization (initial control of seizure) of the baby.

Total initial dose: Total amount of phenobarbitone given as loading doses in both group for initial control of seizure.

Hypoxic Ischemic Encephalopathy stage 2 (HIE stage 2): Any asphyxiated baby will be in HIE stage 2 if there is seizure or high pitch cry plus any one of other 7 signs of stage 2 of Sarnet & Sarnet¹³ classification of hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy which include level of consciousness, muscle tone, posture, tendon reflexes/clonus, myoclonus, moro reflex and pupillary light response.

Data management and analysis:

Data were analyzed by SPSS-20 software for windows. Categorical variables were compared by chi square test and quantitative variable were compared by independent t test.

Results:

A total of 60 neonates, diagnosed as perinatal asphyxia with HIE stage 2 were included and randomized in to two groups, among them 35 (58%) were male and 25 (42%) were female. No statistical significance has been observed regarding mean age at enrollment, sex distribution, antenatal checkup, place of delivery or mode of delivery and duration of labour, duration of delayed cry, birth weight or delivery attendance (Table- I).

Recurrence of seizure occurred in 13% of babies in group A and 10% of babies in group B, which was not statistically significant (Table-II).

Recurrence of seizure occurred in 4 babies in group A and 3 babies in group B. Among them, recurrence occurred within 12 hours in 50% of babies in group-A and 67% of babies in group-B; after 12 hours, seizure recurred in 50% of babies in group-A and 33% of babies in group-B. No recurrence of seizure occurred after 24 hours. No statistically significant difference was found between two groups for seizure recurrence time. Also mean time of seizure recurrence between two groups showed no significant difference (Table- III).

Though significant difference exists in the total initial dose of phenobarbitone between the two groups ($p= 0.03$) but the difference in serum level of phenobarbitone between two groups was not significant (Table- IV).

Table-I: Comparison of base line characteristics between the groups (n=60).

Base line characteristics	Group A n (%)	Group B n (%)	P value
Mean ($\pm$ SD) age (hours)	10.93 $\pm$ 9.06	10.67 $\pm$ 8.79	1.0
Mean ($\pm$ SD) maternal age (years)	22.93 $\pm$ 3.89	23.17 $\pm$ 4.44	0.89
Mean ($\pm$ SD) gestational age (weeks)	38.36 $\pm$ 1.43	37.90 $\pm$ 1.56	0.23
Mean ($\pm$ SD) birth weight in gm	2995.7 $\pm$ 317.2	2905.7 $\pm$ 305	0.19
Mean ($\pm$ SD) duration of labour (hours)	10.0 $\pm$ 4.2	11.7 $\pm$ 5.7	0.18
Mean ($\pm$ SD) delayed cry (min)	21.30 $\pm$ 22.98	18.10 $\pm$ 22.57	0.58
Types of ANC			
Regular	13(43.3%)	15(50.0%)	0.61
Irregular	17(56.7%)	15(50.0%)	
Mode of delivery			
NVD	26(86.7%)	21(70.0%)	0.12
LUCS	4(13.3%)	9(30.0%)	
Place of delivery			
Home	10(33.3%)	5(16.7%)	0.23
Hospital	20(66.7%)	25(83.3%)	
Delivery attended by			
Doctor	14(46.7%)	21(70.0%)	0.11
Nurse	7(23.3%)	6(20.0%)	
Dai	9(30.0%)	3(10.0%)	

n implies to number, unpaired student's *t*-test done for continuous variables and Chi-square test done for categorical variables

Table-II: Comparison of seizure recurrence number between two groups

Recurrence of seizure in number of babies	Group A n (%)	Group B n (%)	p value
Recurrence	4(13.3%)	3(10.0%)	0.68
No recurrence	26(86.7%)	27(90.0%)	

Table- III: Comparison of seizure recurrence time (hours) between two groups

Seizure recurrence time (hours)	Group A n (%)	Group B n (%)	p value
0-12 hours	2(50.0%)	2(66.7%)	0.65
13-24 hours	2(50.0%)	1(33.3%)	
Mean ($\pm$ SD) seizure recurrence time in hour	11.50 $\pm$ 4.36	12.67 $\pm$ 3.06	0.71

Table- IV: Comparison of mean values of total initial dose of phenobarbitone and serum level of phenobarbitone (after last loading dose in group-A and first maintenance dose in group-B) between two groups

Variables	Group A Mean ($\pm$ SD)	Group B Mean ($\pm$ SD)	p value
Total initial dose of Phenobarbitone (mg/kg)	29.00 ($\pm$ 8.03)	33.33 ($\pm$ 6.98)	0.03*
S. Phenobarbitone (μ g/ml)	38.52 ($\pm$ 14.35)	43.10 ($\pm$ 15.79)	0.24*

*Unpaired student's *t*-test

Discussion:

This study included 60 newborns clinically diagnosed as perinatal asphyxia with HIE stage 2. The frequency of male babies was higher than that of female babies (male: female = 1.4:1); other study reported similar male female ratio as observed by Turhan et al.⁹ Most deliveries were conducted at hospital as the study population was selected from the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit of BSMMU and department of neonatology, DMCH, Dhaka. The mode of delivery was not significantly different between group A and group B. The difference in other variables like place of delivery, duration of labor, delayed cry after birth, regular antenatal care (ANC), birth weight, gestational age, maternal age, and delivery attendant (doctor, nurse or dai) were not significant between the groups.

Thirteen percent babies had recurrence of seizures in group A and 10% in group B. Here phenobarbitone was effective in 87% cases in group A and 90% in group B. The difference was not statistically significant. Gal et al. had shown 85% seizures controlled by phenobarbitone in neonatal seizures as a whole i.e. not only in perinatal asphyxia but seizures due to other causes also.¹⁴ Several studies have shown variable effect of barbiturates in treatment of asphyxiated human neonates.¹⁵⁻¹⁸ In our study the recurrence of seizures was very low and there was no statistically significant difference between loading plus maintenance dose and loading dose only. As there was no statistically significant difference in seizure recurrence number and seizure recurrence time between two groups (loading dose only versus loading plus maintenance dose), maintenance dose is presumably unnecessary as seizure was initially controlled by phenobarbitone loading dose only.

In perinatal asphyxia seizure is not a phenomenon but 'epiphenomenon' which means an exceptional symptom in a disease that is not related to the usual course of the disease. When acute encephalopathy is over, seizure is no longer evident; it would not be justifiable to continue the drug (phenobarbitone), as the maintenance dose has no additional benefit. More over this additional drug (daily maintenance dose of phenobarbitone) may cause cumulative effects. So if initially controlled, only loading dose seems to be sufficient for the treatment of neonatal seizure with perinatal

asphyxia with HIE stage 2.

Long term follow-up is necessary though we could not do it in this study due to time and economic constraints. As perinatal asphyxia is a leading cause of neonatal mortality and morbidity further large scale, longer duration, prospective study can give answer to many questions including 'whether the maintenance dose of phenobarbitone will be given in all patients of HIE stage 2 or those of the selected patients'.

Conclusion and Recommendation:

Neonatal seizure of perinatal asphyxia with HIE stage 2 were fully controlled in 87% of babies among group A and 90% babies among group B. There was no statistically significant difference in recurrence of seizures between two groups. So if initially controlled, the maintenance dose of phenobarbitone (after loading dose) is presumably unnecessary to prevent recurrence of neonatal seizures in asphyxiated newborns of HIE stage 2. However, each patient should be taken individually and some points should be kept in consideration: (1) Baby should be otherwise well, (2) Careful clinical observation is mandatory, (3) Re-initiation of anticonvulsive therapy if seizure recurs.

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